

IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF THE GAS LIFT VALVE SEAL**Hamidova G.***Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, teacher***ABSTRACT**

Currently, gas lift valves are widely used in the gas industry to maintain pressure in wells. However, there are often problems with sealing valves, which leads to a loss of efficiency and increased energy consumption. Improving the operability of the sealing element of the gas lift valve will reduce the likelihood of gas leaks and increase the reliability and efficiency of the entire gas lift device. In addition, this will reduce the cost of repairing and replacing faulty sealing elements and improve the economic efficiency of gas production.

The sealing element of the gas lift valve plays a key role in ensuring reliable and efficient operation of this device. A malfunction of the sealing element can lead to a gas leak, which will entail significant financial losses and risks to the safety of personnel and the environment. Therefore, the urgency of improving the operability of the sealing element of the gas lift valve is to ensure the safe and reliable operation of oil and gas equipment, improve the economic efficiency of production and reduce financial losses of companies engaged in gas production and transportation.

THE PURPOSE of the work is to study the provision of a gas lift valve and a check valve with a flexible, sealing element and means to protect the element from deflection or destruction.

Keywords: Gas lift valve, Bellows type, Valve sealing, Composite materials, Fluoroplast-4, Carbon fiber, Socket for the sealing.

The gas lift method of oil extraction is the process of oil extraction, which is carried out by using a mixture of gas and liquid in wells. The gas lift method is one of the most common and effective methods of oil extraction and is used in many places around the world. The basic principle of the gas lift method is to use gas to create a gas cushion that helps lift oil to the surface. To create this cushion, gas is injected into the well, which allows additional pressure to be created, which helps to raise the oil to the surface. The gas lift method is used for oil extraction from a great depth, where traditional methods of oil extraction may be less effective. During the operation of wells, various methods of reducing starting pressures can be used, based on reducing the density of products in the lifting column. The most effective use of starting gas lift valves. A gas lift valve is a device used in a gas lift well to control the flow of gas and liquid. It is important for the gas lift system, because it allows you to regulate the capacity of the well and maintain a stable pressure in the well. Well start-up is carried out using the so-called starting valves, and the gas input during normal operation of the lift is carried out through the so-called working valve. The whole variety of deep valves can be classified according to the following criteria:

- 1 As intended:
starting; working; end.
- 2 By design:
spring; bellows; combined.
- 3 By the nature of the work:
normally open; normally closed.
- 4 By actuation pressure:
from the pressure in the annular space; from the pressure in the lift.

Bellows gas lift valve is one of the types of gas lift valves that is used in wells to regulate the flow of gas and liquid. The bellows is a sealed membrane made of a special material. It connects two chambers inside the valve and serves to control the flow of liquid and gas in the well. When the pressure in the upper chamber rises, the bellows expands, opening the way for liquid and gas to escape through the valve. When the pressure decreases, the bellows contracts and closes the way for the liquid and gas to exit.

The advantage of the bellows gas lift valve is its high reliability and durability. The bellows is made of a special material that is highly resistant to various operating conditions, such as high pressure, temperature and aggressive environments. In addition, the bellows valve does not require constant maintenance and can work for a long time without interruption.

Bellows-type gas lift valves consist of a charging device, a bellows chamber, a rod-seat pair, a check valve and a device for fixing the valve in the borehole chamber.

The bellows chamber is charged with nitrogen through a spool. Bellows chamber is a sealed welded pressure vessel, the main working body of which is a metal multilayer bellows. The rod-seat pair is the shut-off device of the valve to which the gas flows through the windows of the pocket of the borehole chamber. The check valve is designed to prevent the flow of liquid from the lifting pipes into the annulus of the well. Bellows-type gas lift valves are divided into starting and working valves for their intended purpose. The control pressure for the starting valves is the gas pressure of the annular space of the well. Acting on the effective area of the bellows, the gas compresses it, as a result of which the rod rises, and the gas, opening the check valve, enters the lifting pipes. The number of valves to be installed depends on the gas pressure in the well and its depth. They are closed sequentially as the level in the annular space of the well decreases. The lowering of the level in the annulus of the well continues to the depth of the lower (working) valve.

The bellows—type gas lift valve seal is a device that ensures tightness of the connection between the

valve body and the bellows, which is used to compensate for deformations. The seal usually consists of an O-ring and a bellows. The sealing ring is usually made of materials that have good resistance to aggressive environments and high temperatures. These can be various polymers, such as fluoroplastics, polyamides, polyethylene, polypropylene and others.

Valve sealing problems can occur for various reasons. Investigation of these reasons is an important step to improve the efficiency and reliability of gas lift equipment, as well as reduce the cost of its maintenance and repair. One of the main causes of problems with sealing valves is the wear of sealing elements. Sealing elements can wear out due to friction, loads, exposure to chemically aggressive media and high temperatures. The wear of the sealing elements can lead to gas leakage and reduce the efficiency of the gas lift device.

Creation of composite materials that consist of a combination of Fluoroplast-4 and carbon fiber. This can improve the performance and durability of the sealing element, since carbon fiber has high strength, and Fluoroplast-4 resists chemical attack well and has high temperature stability. However, such composite materials require additional research and testing to determine their optimal properties in specific operating conditions of gas lift valves.

Fluoroplast-4 (PTFE) has the following advantages:

1. Excellent chemical resistance
2. low coefficient of friction
3. excellent wear resistance
4. high temperature resistance

Some of the disadvantages of Fluoroplast-4:

1. poor mechanical strength
2. relatively high cost
3. poor electrical conductivity.

Carbon (C) also has its advantages:

1. high strength and rigidity
2. excellent wear resistance
3. low density.

Some of the disadvantages of carbon fiber:

1. poor chemical resistance
2. instability to high temperatures

3. high cost.

Combining Fluoroplast-4 with carbon fiber can help combine the advantages of both materials and eliminate their disadvantages. For example, the use of a carbon matrix with inclusions of Fluoroplast-4 can improve chemical resistance and reduce friction while maintaining high strength. However, such combined materials can be difficult to manufacture and have a high cost. The combination of Fluoroplast-4 and carbon as a composite material can be achieved by producing

a composite using filling technology, where carbon particles are added to a matrix of Fluoroplast-4. Preparation of materials: Fluoroplast-4 and carbon fiber (usually in the form of powder or fibers). Mixing of Fluoroplast-4 and carbon fiber in the right ratio in accordance with the requirements of the project. Pressing the composite material into the desired shape and size. Heat

treatment, which may include heating to a certain temperature and holding at this temperature for polymerization of Fluoroplast-4 and fusion of carbon particles with the matrix.

Schematic formation of graphite structure:

Technical characteristics of the material:

- Tensile strength: from 50 to 200 MPa
- Coefficient of thermal expansion: from 2 to 10 microns/m*K
- Operating temperature range: -50 to +150 °C
- Density: from 1.6 to 2.0 g/cm³;
- Compressive strength: from 70 to 150 MPa
- Modulus of elasticity: from 5 to 15 GPa
- Coefficient of thermal expansion: from 1.5 to 2.5*10⁻⁶ to⁻¹

- Degree of heat resistance: up to 250 degrees Celsius

- Chemical resistance: good

Depending on the type of composite materials connection, the shape of the socket for the sealing element will change. Changing the design of the sealing ring and seal will increase the operability of the valve itself.

The sealing element in the gas lift valve is usually located on the spindle or on the axis of the gate. This part of the valve on which the sealing element is located is called the valve seat or seat seal. The valve seat is the surface on which the sealing element presses, ensuring the tightness of the valve when closing. Usually the valve seat is made of materials that have high wear resistance and corrosion resistance. It can be made either as a separate element or integrated into the valve body. The seat can be made from a variety of materials, depending on the specific requirements of the valve. Common materials used for valve seats include metals such as stainless steel, tungsten carbide, and nickel alloy, as well as ceramics and polymers. The choice of material depends on the fluid being pumped, the operating temperature and pressure, and the expected wear and corrosion resistance. The seat may be integral to the valve body, or it may be a separate component that can be replaced. In some cases, the seat may be designed as a replaceable cartridge that can be easily removed and replaced, simplifying maintenance and reducing downtime. The shape of the seat is critical to the performance of the valve. The seat must be machined to the correct shape and dimensions to ensure proper sealing and to avoid damage to the sealing element. Typically, the seat is a conical or spherical shape that matches the shape of the sealing element, creating a tight seal when the valve is closed. The angle of the cone or sphere can vary depending on the specific valve design.

In summary, the seat of a gas lift valve is an essential component that ensures proper sealing and safe operation of the valve. It can be made from a variety of materials and may be a separate component or integral to the valve body. The shape of the seat is critical to the performance of the valve, and it must be machined to precise dimensions to ensure proper sealing and avoid damage to the sealing element.

CONCLUSIONS.

The main objectives of the work were to study the mechanical properties of such a combination of materials, as well as to determine the optimal parameters for obtaining composite materials with maximum strength and durability, which will improve the characteristics of the sealing elements of gas lift valves, which will lead to an increase in the operating time of the valve itself.

The results of the study showed that the combination of composite elements of fluoroplast-4 with carbon leads to an improvement in the mechanical properties of the material. In particular, it was found that the addition of carbon to fluoroplast-4 increases its strength and rigidity, as well as reduces the tendency to fracture due to fatigue. In addition, the resulting composite materials were resistant to high temperatures and chemical aggressive environments.

Thus, it can be concluded that the combination of composite elements of fluoroplast-4 with carbon is an effective way to obtain composite materials with high strength and durability. The results of the work can be used in various industries where high strength and stability of materials are required.

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